

OZONE FORMATION AND THE PRODUCTION OF THE

JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN

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Ozone formation has been studied under conditions optimum for the production of the Joshi effect Δi in oxygen. Output of O_3 is small. It is independent of the exciting potential and increases with its frequency f . Δi is markedly potential-sensitive and decreases with f . It is concluded therefore that no relationship exists between O_3 output and Δi .

In studies of the Joshi effect Δi in oxygen a complication, which is non-existent in other gases showing Δi , arises from the fact that allotropes of higher molecular weight like ozone and oxozone are formed when the gas is subjected to the silent discharge. Whilst oxozone formation under any condition is negligible, the formation of ozone under certain conditions is appreciable (Vosmaer, "Ozone", Constable, London, 1916; Rideal, "Ozone", Constable, London, 1920), and deserves serious notice. It was of interest therefore to investigate the correlation, if any, between the two phenomena in oxygen, viz., ozone formation and production of the Joshi effect.

Oxygen gas, enclosed in a Siemens' tube at different pressures p and temperatures t was subjected to discharge at various applied potentials V of 50 and 500 cycles frequency f . The duration of discharge in each case was 60 minutes. The gas thereafter was bubbled slowly through a neutral solution of potassium iodide contained in three washers in series. Iodine, liberated according to the equation

was titrated, after acidification with dilute sulphuric acid, against standard thiosulphate using starch as the internal indicator (Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1935). A typical set of results is shown below.

TABLE I

Vol. of electrode space of ozoniser = 65.5 c.c.				
V (Kilovolts, r. m. s)	f (cyc./sec.)	p (mm. Hg)	t	Ozone output (mg.).
4.98	50	331	27°-28°	0.515
3.23	50	"	"	0.530
4.58	50	"	"	0.530
5.33	50	"	"	0.515
6.77	500	"	"	0.624
3.73	50	100	"	0.264
"	50	205	"	0.396
"	50	298	"	0.475
"	50	402	"	0.554
"	50	331	40°-41°	0.187

That, as seen from the foregoing results, the amount of ozone formed, under the above experimental conditions, which are essentially similar to those under which Δi is observed, is evident from the following considerations:

(1) Thomson and Threlfall (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1886, 40, 340) and Warburg (*Ann. Physik*, 1905, 17, 1) have shown that the formation of ozone in the silent discharge is associated with the production of a luminous glow which succeeds ionisation. Optimum yields are obtained when the luminosity of the glow is at a maximum (Rideal, *op. cit.*, pp. 95, 96). In the above experiments, on the other hand, the glow was very feeble.

The glow under conditions of maximum proportional Δi is so feeble that to get a tolerably measurable impression of its spectrum on a plate, Deo (*Phil. Mag.*, 1948, **39**, 978) working with chlorine had to give an exposure of 300 hours.

(2) The concentration of ozone and yields obtainable per kilowatt hour increase with the pressure of oxygen, though not indefinitely. von Wartenberg and Max (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, **14**, 879) obtained maximum ozone concentration and yield when the pressure of the gas was about one atmosphere. The pressures employed above are, however, smaller than the atmospheric pressure.

(3) The yield of ozone increases with the rate of flow of oxygen. The condition most favourable for ozone formation is low ozone concentration or relatively high rate of flow of the gas.

Since the above experiments are, however, static, the limiting concentration of ozone is very small. After this state is reached, there is no further increase in the concentration of ozone, the rate of formation dO_3/dt becoming equal to the rate of its destruction by a catalytic and other effects.

The possibilities of synthesis and decomposition of ozone under light have also to be considered. Lenard (*Ann. Physik*, 1900, **1**, 486) found that, at ordinary gas pressures, only the extreme ultraviolet, below 2000 Å, causes ozonisation of oxygen. Δi in oxygen has been observed under visible and the near ultraviolet (Mohanty and Kamath, this *Journal*, 1948, **28**, 467; Mohanty, *ibid.*, 1948, **28**, 555). The probability of photoformation of ozone does not therefore arise. Ozone, on the other hand, is decomposed by visible light (Griffith and Shutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1948). This would increase the conductivity (Pinkus and Ruysen, *Bull. soc. chim. Belg.*, 1928, **37**, 304). The observed decrease in current cannot therefore arise from any photochemical action of the radiations employed.

The above results show that the amount of ozone formed is practically independent of V , provided $V > V_m$ the 'threshold potential' at which the glow starts; this is in agreement with the findings of Warburg (*Ann. Physik*, 1904, **13**, 464) and Gray (*ibid.*, 1904, **13**, 477). The Joshi effect, on the other hand, is markedly potential-sensitive (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*). It is not observed below V_m . Above V_m , the net effect increases with V to a maximum and then decreases. The relative effect, on the other hand, is maximum near V_m and decreases thereafter. Data in the table also show that, in agreement with earlier work of Fröhlich (*Elektrotech. Z.*, 1901, **12**, 340), Warburg and Leithauser (*Ann. Physik*, 1909, **4**, 28, 17), Lechner (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1911, **17**, 414; 1915, **21**, 309) and Puschin and Kauchtshev (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **46**, 576), ozone output increases with f . The magnitude of Δi , both net and proportional, on the other hand, decreases with f (Mohanty, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1949, Part III, Abst. No. 25). It would appear therefore that there is no correspondence between the amount of ozone formed and the magnitude of Δi in oxygen. It is not possible to draw any conclusion from the pressure and temperature variation of ozone output, since both this and Δi increase with p and $1/t$.

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